

Research Data Management Policy

Polymer Concepts in Cellular Function

Version 1.1

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Contents

1 Preamble	3
1.1 Purpose of this policy	3
1.2 Commitment to transparency, honesty, reproducibility	3
1.3 Relationship to Good Research Practice	3
1.4 Commitment to FAIR principles	4
2 Jurisdiction	5
2.1 Scope of application	5
2.2 What constitutes research data	5
2.3 Temporal scope	5
2.4 Adoption and review	6
2.5 Relationship to institutional policies	6
2.6 Applicable regulations and codes of conduct	6
3 Rights and Ownership	8
3.1 Data rights and responsibilities	8
3.2 Intellectual property	8
3.3 Agreements on usage rights	8
3.4 Licenses	9
3.5 Third-party data	9
3.6 Data rights upon change of institution	10
4 Documentation and Quality Assurance	11
4.1 Documentation requirements	11
4.2 Metadata standards	12
4.3 Documenting negative results	12
4.4 Quality assurance procedures	12
5 Handling Research Data	13
5.1 Planning	13
5.1.1 Data Management Plan (DMP)	13
5.1.2 Reuse potential of existing data	13
5.1.3 Data types and formats	13
5.1.4 Storage and resource planning	14
5.1.5 Roles and responsibilities	14
5.2 Collection	14
5.2.1 Discipline-specific standards	14
5.2.2 File formats	14
5.2.3 File naming and organization	14
5.2.4 Technical metadata	15
5.2.5 Version control	15

5.3	Analysis	15
5.3.1	Reproducible workflows	15
5.3.2	Software documentation	15
5.3.3	Source code management	15
5.4	Preservation	16
5.4.1	Retention period	16
5.4.2	Storage location	16
5.4.3	File formats for long-term preservation	16
5.4.4	What to preserve	16
5.5	Sharing	16
5.5.1	Open Access principle	16
5.5.2	Repositories	17
5.5.3	Timing of data publication	17
5.5.4	Persistent identifiers	17
5.5.5	Licensing for shared data	17
5.6	Reuse	17
5.6.1	Enabling reuse	17
5.6.2	Citing reused data	18
5.6.3	Respecting original licenses and IPR	18
6	Data Safety and Security	19
6.1	Backup and recovery	19
6.2	Access control	19
6.3	Protection against manipulation	19
7	Responsibilities, Rights, and Duties	21
7.1	Principal Investigators	21
7.2	Researchers	21
7.3	Research Data Steward	21
	Appendices	22
	Appendix A: CRC1551 Consortium	22
	Appendix B: Definitions	24
	Appendix C: Abbreviations	26
	Appendix D: Suggested Directory Structure and File Naming	27
	Appendix E: Recommended File Formats	29
	Appendix F: Core Metadata Standard	30
	Appendix G: Version History	32
	Appendix H: Publication Checklist	34
	References	35

1 Preamble

1.1 Purpose of this policy

This policy establishes the principles, requirements, and recommendations for Research Data Management (RDM) within Collaborative Research Centre (CRC) 1551 “Polymer Concepts in Cellular Function”, funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG). It provides a common framework of rules and governance for all consortium members across participating institutions to ensure that research data is managed consistently, responsibly, and in compliance with funder and institutional requirements.

The policy aims to:

- ensure the integrity and reproducibility of research conducted within CRC1551
- support researchers in meeting their obligations under Good Research Practice
- facilitate collaboration and data exchange within the consortium
- enable long-term preservation and reuse of research data in accordance with the FAIR principles

This policy is a living document maintained by the Research Data Steward (RDS). Its continued relevance will be evaluated at regular intervals, and updates will be made as needed to reflect evolving requirements and best practices.

1.2 Commitment to transparency, honesty, reproducibility

CRC1551 is committed to the fundamental values of scientific research: transparency, honesty, and reproducibility. These values, as set out in the DFG Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice [1], guide all aspects of research data management within the consortium.

Transparency requires that research processes, methods, and data are documented and communicated openly, enabling others to understand and scrutinise the work.

Honesty demands that data is collected, analysed, and reported accurately and without manipulation, and that the contributions of others are properly acknowledged.

Reproducibility requires that research is conducted and documented in a manner that allows others to understand, verify, and build upon the findings.

These principles apply to all stages of the **research data lifecycle** and to all members of the consortium.

1.3 Relationship to Good Research Practice

Research data management is an integral part of Good Research Practice (Gute wissenschaftliche Praxis). This policy implements the requirements set out in the DFG Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice [1], which **are binding for all DFG-funded research**.

Members of CRC1551 are additionally bound by the Good Research Practice regulations of their respective institutions:

- Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz [2]
- IMB gGmbH [3]
- Max Planck Society [4]

- University of Stuttgart [5]
- University of Würzburg [6]

This policy complements but does not replace these institutional regulations. **In cases of conflict, the stricter requirement applies.**

1.4 Commitment to FAIR principles

FAIR principles are an integral part of Good Research Practice. Research data should be:

- **Findable:** Data and metadata are assigned **persistent identifiers** and registered in searchable resources.
- **Accessible:** Data can be retrieved using standardised protocols, with metadata remaining accessible even when data is restricted.
- **Interoperable:** Data and metadata use formal, shared vocabularies and formats that enable integration with other data.
- **Reusable:** Data is well-documented, clearly licensed, and meets domain-relevant standards to enable future reuse.

The FAIR principles guide the practices and recommendations throughout this policy. **All consortium members must apply the FAIR principles to their research data.** Applying FAIR principles does not require that all data be openly accessible; rather, data should be “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”.

2 Jurisdiction

2.1 Scope of application

This policy applies to all members of CRC1551, including:

- Principal Investigators
- Postdoctoral researchers
- Doctoral researchers
- Student research assistants involved in research activities
- Technical and administrative staff contributing to research

The policy covers all research data generated, collected, or processed within CRC1551-funded projects, regardless of the institutional affiliation of the individual researcher.

When collaborating with external partners, **consortium members are responsible for ensuring that the standards defined in this policy are maintained.** Specific arrangements should be documented in collaboration agreements.

2.2 What constitutes research data

Research data comprises all data generated, collected, or processed in the course of research activities. Within CRC1551, this includes but is not limited to:

- Experimental raw data
- Processed and analysed data
- Simulations and computational results
- Software, scripts, and code developed for data acquisition or analysis
- Protocols, methods, and workflows
- Samples and physical research materials
- Metadata and documentation describing the above

A detailed definition of key terms, including what is explicitly not covered by this policy, is provided in Appendix B.

2.3 Temporal scope

This policy applies to all research data generated from the date of its adoption by the CRC1551 consortium. It remains in effect for the duration of CRC1551 and continues to apply to data generated during this time even after CRC1551 concludes.

Obligations under this policy persist beyond an individual's membership in the consortium. Researchers who leave the consortium remain bound by the requirements concerning data they generated or managed during their involvement, particularly regarding retention periods and accessibility.

Before leaving the consortium, researchers must ensure proper handover of data and documentation to their Principal Investigator or a designated successor.

2.4 Adoption and review

Version 1.0 of this policy was accepted by the CRC1551 consortium through an opt-out procedure. All consortium PIs were given the opportunity to review the policy within a defined review period. No concerns were raised.

This policy is reviewed at least every 12 months. An extraordinary review takes place if relevant framework conditions change, in particular requirements of the DFG or applicable policies of the participating institutions.

2.5 Relationship to institutional policies

Consortium members are affiliated with different institutions, each with their own research data management policies and codes of conduct. This policy provides a common framework for the consortium but does not replace institutional obligations.

Members must comply with both this policy and the regulations of their home institution:

- Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz [2, 7]
- IMB gGmbH [3, 8]
- Max Planck Society [4]
- University of Stuttgart [9]
- University of Würzburg [6, 10]

Institutional policies are legally binding and take precedence over this CRC1551 policy. **Where requirements differ but do not conflict, the stricter standard applies.** In cases of genuine conflict between institutional and CRC1551 requirements, members should consult their Principal Investigator or the RDS for guidance.

2.6 Applicable regulations and codes of conduct

The following regulations and codes of conduct form the compliance framework for research data management within CRC1551:

Funder requirements (binding for all members):

- DFG Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice [1]
- DFG Guidelines on the Handling of Research Data [11]

Institutional regulations (binding for the respective members):

- JGU Regulations for Ensuring Good Research Practice [2]
- JGU Research Data Management Guidelines [7]
- IMB Policy for Safeguarding Good Research Practice [3]
- IMB Research Data Management Policy [8]
- MPG Rules of Good Scientific Practice [4]
- University of Stuttgart Code of Conduct [5]
- University of Stuttgart Research Data Policy [9]
- University of Würzburg Code of Good Practice in Research [6]

- [University of Würzburg Research Data Management Guidelines \[10\]](#)

Guidance documents (recommended):

- [FAIRmat Guide to Writing a Research Data Management Plan \[12\]](#)
- [FAIRmat Guide to Legal Aspects in Research Data Management \[13\]](#)

3 Rights and Ownership

3.1 Data rights and responsibilities

Research data generated within CRC1551 is produced using public funding and institutional resources. The rights and responsibilities associated with this data are shared among multiple parties.

The primary responsibility for research data lies with the researcher who generates or collects it. This includes the obligation to document, store, and manage the data according to this policy and applicable institutional regulations.

Principal Investigators bear overall responsibility for research data generated within their projects. They must ensure that data remains accessible and properly managed, including beyond the employment period of individual researchers.

The institutions employing the researchers typically hold usage rights to the data, subject to the regulations of the respective institution and any applicable agreements. Researchers retain the right to use data they generated for their own continued research, subject to institutional regulations.

3.2 Intellectual property

Research within CRC1551 produces various types of outputs. Whether intellectual property rights (IPR) apply depends on the nature of the output and requires case-by-case consideration.

Raw data (e.g., machine-generated measurements such as NMR spectra, CD spectra, sequencing reads): Typically not protected by copyright, as they are considered facts rather than intellectual creations.

Processed data, figures, and visualisations (e.g., graphs, micrographs, tables, annotated images): May be protected by copyright if they represent a scientific or technical description showing a degree of originality and individuality.

Structures and sequences (e.g., novel protein structures): Scientific discoveries are not protected by IPR. Once deposited in public databases (e.g., Protein Data Bank), they become part of the scientific commons.

Software and code (e.g., analysis scripts, simulation programs): Protected by copyright if they represent the author's own intellectual creation. This protection applies to all forms of expression including drafts and preparatory material. Distribution and reproduction require the consent of the rights holder.

Publications and written works: Protected by copyright. Authors typically grant publishers certain usage rights upon publication.

Patentable inventions: Governed by the German Employee Invention Act (Arbeitnehmererfindungsgesetz) and institutional regulations. **Researchers must report potentially patentable inventions to their institution before any public disclosure, including conference presentations or preprints.**

3.3 Agreements on usage rights

Early in a project, the parties involved should agree on:

- who may use the data during and after the project
- how the data may be shared and published
- how contributions will be acknowledged
- what happens to the data when researchers leave

These agreements should be documented in writing. For collaborations within CRC1551, informal agreements (e.g., by email) may suffice for routine cases. For collaborations with external partners or in cases involving sensitive data or commercial interests, formal agreements should be established.

When in doubt, researchers should consult their Principal Investigator or the RDS.

3.4 Licenses

Licenses define the terms under which others may use, modify, and redistribute data and software. Applying a license removes ambiguity and enables reuse. If no license is applied, others cannot legally reuse the work, even if it is publicly accessible. Researchers should choose a license that is as permissive as possible to maximise reuse potential.

For research data, the Creative Commons (CC) framework is widely used:

- [CC0 \(Public Domain Dedication\)](#): No restrictions; recommended for maximum reusability
- [CC-BY \(Attribution 4.0 International\)](#): Requires citation of the original source

Other CC licenses are available if specific restrictions are required.

For software and code, open source licenses are recommended:

- MIT: Most flexible; permits broad reuse with minimal restrictions
- Apache 2.0: Includes explicit provisions for patents and contributions; requires modifications to be documented; suitable for projects with multiple contributors or requiring clear legal protections

Researchers should ensure that the chosen license is compatible with any third-party data or code incorporated into their work. When depositing data or code in repositories, repository-specific licensing requirements should be checked.

3.5 Third-party data

When using data from external sources in publications or presentations, **researchers must respect the rights and terms associated with the original work.**

Before using third-party data, researchers must:

- verify that the intended use is permitted by the license or terms of use
- ensure proper attribution as required by the source
- check for any restrictions on redistribution or modification
- document the source, license, and access date

Data obtained under restrictive licenses or through access agreements may not be suitable for open sharing. In such cases, researchers should clearly document these limitations in their data management plan and any resulting publications.

When in doubt about the permissibility of a specific use, researchers must contact the original data provider or consult the RDS.

3.6 Data rights upon change of institution

When researchers leave CRC1551 or change institutions, **the rights and responsibilities regarding research data must be clarified.**

Data generated within CRC1551 projects must remain accessible to the consortium. Before leaving, researchers must:

- **ensure all data is properly documented and stored according to this policy**
- **hand over data and documentation to their Principal Investigator or a designated successor**
- clarify with their PI and, if necessary, their institution which data they may take and continue to use

Researchers retain the right to use data they generated for their own continued research, subject to institutional regulations and any agreements made under Section 3.3.

Principal Investigators are responsible for ensuring continuity of data access when group members leave.

4 Documentation and Quality Assurance

4.1 Documentation requirements

All research activities **must be documented in sufficient detail to allow others to understand, evaluate, and reproduce the work.**

Documentation **must include:**

- **who performed the work**
- **what data was collected or generated, and when**
- **how the data was collected (instruments, settings, protocols)**
- **how the data was processed and analysed**

Documentation should include:

- the research hypothesis under which the data was collected
- significant decisions made during the research process

Documentation **must be created contemporaneously with the research, not retrospectively,** and **must be stored securely and remain accessible for the duration of the retention period.**

To support FAIR data principles and prevent loss of documentation, **electronic documentation is mandatory.** Accepted forms include:

- institutional or domain-specific electronic lab notebooks (e.g., elabFTW, Chemotion)
- custom file-based documentation systems maintained on backed-up institutional storage

Good Practice

One experiment record per experiment. Each experiment should have its own dedicated, self-contained record that captures everything needed to repeat it: who performed it and when; the sample identity and preparation history; instrument settings, calibration status, and software version; the location and name of the resulting data file(s); and any deviations from the standard protocol. This record must be findable without searching through chronological notes.

Use templates. Define a standard template for each recurring experiment type at the start of the project and reuse it consistently. Templates ensure completeness and make it easy for new group members to document correctly from day one.

A daily journal is a useful place to record observations, decisions, failed attempts, and ideas as they happen. However, journal entries are chronological and fragmented by nature. Any experiment documented in a daily journal must also have a corresponding structured experiment record. Cross-reference the experiment record from the journal entry so all daily context for a given experiment remains traceable.

Suggested Electronic Laboratory Notebook (ELN) tools:

- **elabFTW** is available to members at JGU and IMB gGmbH. It supports both journal-style entries and structured experiment records with custom templates, file attachments, and entry locking to protect completed records from modification.
- **Chemotion** is designed for chemical synthesis workflows and provides structured data entry

for reactions and compounds with direct repository integration.

- **Labfolder** is available to members of [MPG](#) institutes. The [MPG](#) holds an institutional licence covering all researchers at Max Planck institutes.
- **File-based systems** (a folder per experiment, a README or metadata file capturing the key parameters, data files following the group's naming convention) are a viable alternative for any group. Such a solution has to be stored on a fully backed-up system such as an institutional network drive.

4.2 Metadata standards

Metadata describes the context, content, and structure of research data. Good metadata is essential for data to be findable, understood, and reused.

Researchers should describe their datasets using the [Schema.org Dataset](#) schema as a common baseline. Where a more specific community schema exists for the relevant discipline, that schema should be used in preference. An example for life sciences data is the [Bioschemas profiles framework](#).

The metadata standard and template used by CRC1551 are provided in Appendix F.

4.3 Documenting negative results

Results that do not support the original hypothesis or expected outcome must be documented with the same rigour as positive results [1]. Selective documentation or reporting of only favourable results constitutes a violation of [Good Research Practice](#).

Negative results must be retained and should be made available alongside other research data where appropriate.

4.4 Quality assurance procedures

Researchers are responsible for ensuring the quality of their data throughout the research process [1]. **Quality assurance measures must be applied during data collection, processing, and analysis.**

Appropriate measures include:

- calibration of instruments according to manufacturer or discipline-specific standards
- use of controls and standards in experiments
- validation of analysis methods and software
- verification of data integrity after transfer or conversion
- peer review of methods, code, and results within the research group

When research findings are made publicly available, the quality assurance methods applied should be documented and, where appropriate, described in the publication.

5 Handling Research Data

5.1 Planning

Effective data management begins during the project initiation phase to ensure resources are allocated appropriately.

Data Management Plan (DMP)

A **Data Management Plan** (DMP) describes how research data will be handled during and after a project. **All CRC1551 subprojects must create a DMP at the start of the project** [1]. A DMP can take any form as long as it complies with DFG requirements.

DMPs should be created using the CRC1551 catalogue hosted in the [JGU RDMO instance](#). Alternative RDMO instances, such as those provided by participating institutions or NFDI consortia, may also be used. The RDS can provide support and templates.

A DMP must be treated as a living document and updated as the project evolves. For researchers enrolled in a doctoral programme, the existence and status of the DMP must be reviewed as part of Thesis Advisory Committee (TAC) meetings.

Good Practice

Start early, fill what you know. Create your DMP in the CRC1551 catalogue on the [JGU RDMO instance](#) before data collection begins. You do not need to answer every question upfront — fill in what is known at project start and leave the rest to be completed as the project progresses.

Update at defined trigger points. A DMP written at project start and never revised does not reflect reality. Update it when: the scope of data collection changes significantly; a new data type or instrument is added; a key team member leaves; or data is prepared for publication.

For doctoral researchers: Check the current status of the DMP before each TAC meeting and update it if necessary.

When leaving the consortium: Ensure the DMP is up to date and hand it over to your PI together with the data. A current DMP is essential for anyone taking over responsibility for the dataset.

Reuse potential of existing data

Before generating new data, researchers should consider whether existing datasets could address their research questions. Reusing existing data avoids unnecessary duplication of effort and can enable new insights through combination with newly generated data.

Relevant sources include discipline-specific repositories, institutional data collections, and data published alongside previous CRC1551 publications.

Data types and formats

During project planning, researchers should identify the types of data they expect to generate and select appropriate file formats.

Open, non-proprietary formats should be preferred as they support long-term accessibility and interoperability. Where proprietary formats are unavoidable, researchers should plan for conversion to

open formats or ensure that the proprietary format remains widely supported for the duration of the retention period.

A list of recommended formats for data types common in CRC1551 is provided in Appendix E.

Storage and resource planning

Researchers should estimate their storage requirements early in the project and ensure that adequate infrastructure is available.

Considerations include:

- expected data volume and growth over time
- need for backup and redundancy
- access requirements for collaborators
- data security and protection against unauthorised access
- costs associated with storage and long-term preservation

Institutional storage services should be used where available. The RDS can advise on suitable options across participating institutions.

Roles and responsibilities

At the start of a project, **it must be clear who is responsible for data management tasks**. This includes responsibility for documentation, backup, quality assurance, and eventual archiving or publication of data.

For collaborative projects involving multiple groups or institutions, **these responsibilities must be agreed upon and documented in the DMP**.

5.2 Collection

The collection phase transforms scientific observation into structured, high-quality information.

Discipline-specific standards

Data collection should follow established methods and protocols relevant to the research discipline. Where community standards exist, **these must be applied** to ensure consistency and comparability of results [1].

File formats

Open, non-proprietary file formats should be used where possible to support long-term accessibility and interoperability. Where proprietary formats are required by instruments or software, **researchers must retain raw data in the original format** and should additionally create copies in open formats where feasible.

A list of recommended formats for data types common in CRC1551 is provided in Appendix E.

File naming and organization

Researchers must establish consistent file naming conventions and folder structures at the start of a project and apply them throughout. Consistent organisation improves data findability, reduces errors, and facilitates handover.

File names should be descriptive, avoid special characters and spaces, and include relevant information such as date, sample identifier, or experiment number.

A recommended directory structure and file naming scheme is provided in Appendix D.

Technical metadata

Technical metadata describing the conditions of data collection must be recorded at the time of acquisition. This includes instrument settings, calibration status, environmental conditions, and software versions.

Where instruments generate metadata automatically, **researchers must verify that this information is captured and stored alongside the experimental metadata.**

Version control

When data or files are modified, **a clear versioning system must be used to track changes.** This allows previous versions to be identified and retrieved if necessary.

For code and scripts, version control systems such as Git should be used. Hosting repositories on a remote platform additionally enables collaboration and provides an off-site backup. CRC1551 members have access to GitLab instances provided by JGU and MPG.

5.3 Analysis

The analysis phase transforms raw data into scientific insights. Transparent and reproducible workflows are essential to ensure that results can be verified and built upon.

Reproducible workflows

Analysis steps must be documented in sufficient detail to allow reproduction of results. This includes recording the sequence of operations, parameters used, and any manual interventions.

Where possible, analysis should be performed using scripts or automated workflows rather than manual processing, as these provide an inherent record of the steps taken and reduce the risk of undocumented variation between runs.

Software documentation

All software used in data analysis must be documented, including the name, version, and relevant settings or parameters.

For commercial software, **license information must be recorded.** For custom scripts and code, **dependencies and runtime environment must be documented** (e.g., operating system, programming language version, required libraries).

Source code management

Code developed for data analysis should be managed using version control systems such as Git. This enables tracking of changes, collaboration, and recovery of previous versions.

When code contributes to published results, **it must be archived in a repository and assigned a persistent identifier (e.g., DOI) to ensure long-term accessibility and citability.**

5.4 Preservation

Proper preservation ensures that research data remains accessible and usable beyond the active phase of a project.

Retention period

Research data must be retained for a minimum of ten years from the date of publication or, if unpublished, from the date of data generation [1].

Longer retention periods may be appropriate for data of particular scientific or historical value, and should be considered where this is foreseeable at the time of archiving.

Storage location

Data must be stored in institutional or discipline-specific repositories that ensure long-term accessibility. Personal devices and local storage are not suitable for long-term preservation.

CRC1551 members should use the storage infrastructure provided by their home institution. The RDS can advise on suitable options across participating institutions.

File formats for long-term preservation

Data intended for long-term preservation must be stored in open, standardised formats to ensure readability beyond the active project phase. Proprietary formats are discouraged for archival purposes.

Where data must be retained in proprietary formats, **researchers must document the software name and version required to access the data.**

What to preserve

At minimum, the following must be preserved for the duration of the retention period:

- **raw data as originally collected**
- **documentation and metadata describing the data**
- **processed data used to derive published results**
- **analysis code and workflows necessary to reproduce results**

Not all intermediate files need to be retained. Researchers should assess and document which data are essential for verification and reuse, and which may be discarded.

5.5 Sharing

Sharing research data enables verification of results, facilitates new discoveries, and maximises the return on public investment in research.

Open Access principle

Open Access to research data underlying publications must be ensured wherever possible [1].

The principle **“as open as possible, as closed as necessary”** applies.

Legitimate reasons for restricting access include protection of personal data, third-party rights, commercial interests, or security concerns. Where restrictions apply, **they must be documented and kept to the minimum necessary.**

Repositories

Data must be deposited in appropriate repositories to ensure discoverability and long-term access. When selecting a repository, researchers should consider the following order of preference:

- discipline-specific repositories (preferred where they exist)
- institutional repositories (e.g., Gutenberg Open Science, EDMOND)
- general-purpose repositories (e.g., Zenodo)

The [Registry of Research Data Repositories](#) provides an overview of available discipline-specific repositories. The RDS can advise on suitable repositories for specific data types.

Timing of data publication

Data underlying published results must be made available no later than the time of publication of the associated findings [1]. Earlier sharing is encouraged where appropriate.

Embargo periods may be applied to protect priority for publication. Such embargoes should be kept as short as possible and must not extend beyond the date of publication of the associated findings.

Persistent identifiers

Published datasets must be assigned a persistent identifier (PID) such as a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) to ensure long-term citability and unambiguous linkage between data and publications.

Most repositories assign persistent identifiers automatically upon deposit. Where this is not the case, **researchers must ensure a persistent identifier is obtained before citing the dataset in a publication.**

Licensing for shared data

All shared data must be assigned a clear license to communicate the terms of reuse. Without a license, potential users cannot legally reuse the data even if it is publicly accessible.

The licensing recommendations in [Section 3.4](#) apply. For most CRC1551 research data, CC0 or [CC-BY \(Attribution 4.0 International\)](#) are the appropriate choices.

5.6 Reuse

The value of research data is multiplied when it can be reused for new purposes. Enabling reuse is the ultimate goal of FAIR data management.

Enabling reuse

Data should be prepared and documented with future reuse in mind. This means using widely understood formats, providing comprehensive metadata, and including sufficient documentation for others to understand and work with the data without needing to contact the original researchers.

Where possible, data and metadata should be made machine-readable to enable automated discovery, validation, and integration with other datasets.

Where data is deposited in a repository, **researchers must verify that the metadata record is complete and that the dataset is correctly described before finalising the deposit.**

Citing reused data

When reusing data created by others, researchers must provide proper attribution. Data citations must include the creator, title, repository, persistent identifier, and access date.

Data citations must be included in the reference list of publications, not only in acknowledgements.

Respecting original licenses and IPR

Researchers reusing third-party data must comply with the terms of the original license. This includes respecting any restrictions on redistribution, modification, or commercial use.

If the license terms are unclear or potentially incompatible with the intended use, **researchers must contact the original data provider for clarification before proceeding.**

6 Data Safety and Security

6.1 Backup and recovery

Research data must be backed up regularly to protect against accidental loss or hardware failure.

Institutional network storage with automated backup must be used as the primary storage location wherever it is available. If local drives or portable devices are used, **researchers must follow the 3-2-1 backup scheme: maintain at least three copies of data, on two different types of storage media, with at least one copy stored off-site or in a geographically separate location.**

Backups must be tested periodically to verify that data can be successfully recovered. A backup that has never been tested cannot be relied upon.

Good Practice

Know what is backed up automatically and what is not. Institutional network storage is typically backed up automatically. Local drives, external hard drives, and portable devices are not. Check with your local IT service which systems are covered.

Keep important data on institutional storage. Raw data, processed data underlying results, and documentation must reside on institutional network storage, not on local drives or laptops. This is the only way to guarantee that automated backups cover your data.

Test your backup. If you store any data on local drives or laptops, ensure you have a backup and test it: locate a backed-up file, restore it to a different location, and verify its integrity. A backup that has never been tested cannot be relied upon.

6.2 Access control

Access to systems used to collect and process research data must be restricted to authorised individuals. Researchers **must:**

- **use strong, unique passwords for all systems containing research data**
- **not share login credentials**
- use a password manager to manage credentials securely

When sharing data with collaborators, researchers should select an access method that limits permissions to what is necessary for the collaboration.

6.3 Protection against manipulation

The integrity of research data must be protected against accidental or deliberate modification.

Practical measures include:

- marking raw data files as read-only after collection to prevent accidental overwriting
- documenting any corrections to data transparently, preserving the original record

Good Practice

Mark raw data as read-only immediately after collection. On Windows, right-click the file or folder, select Properties, and check the Read-only attribute. On Linux/macOS, use `chmod a-w <filename>`. This prevents accidental overwriting while keeping the file accessible for analysis.

Never edit raw data directly. Always work on a copy. Keep the original file untouched and clearly labelled (e.g. with a `_raw` suffix or in a dedicated `raw/` folder marked read-only).

Document corrections transparently. If an error in a dataset must be corrected, do not silently overwrite the original. Record what was changed, why, and when — in the [ELN](#) entry, a README file, or a version-controlled changelog. The original record must remain retrievable.

7 Responsibilities, Rights, and Duties

7.1 Principal Investigators

Principal Investigators (PIs) bear overall responsibility for research data management within their projects and groups. This includes:

- ensuring that group members are aware of and comply with this policy and applicable institutional requirements
- providing adequate time and resources for proper data management
- supervising and supporting early-career researchers in RDM practices
- ensuring that group members have access to relevant RDM training
- ensuring that data remains accessible and properly managed beyond the employment period of individual researchers
- arranging for proper handover of data and documentation when group members leave

7.2 Researchers

Each researcher is responsible for the data they generate and manage. This includes:

- following this policy and applicable institutional codes of conduct
- documenting data and processes according to the standards set out in this policy
- storing and backing up data appropriately
- ensuring data is accessible to authorised colleagues and the PI
- completing proper handover of data and documentation when leaving the CRC

7.3 Research Data Steward

The Research Data Steward (RDS) provides guidance and support on research data management matters within CRC1551. Responsibilities include:

- advising researchers and PIs on RDM practices, tools, and standards
- serving as liaison between institutional research data management services, PIs, and researchers on RDM topics
- organising RDM training and awareness activities for CRC members
- maintaining the CRC1551 RDMO catalogue and recommending suitable tools and workflows
- keeping this policy up to date and developing SOPs in consultation with PIs

The RDS supports but does not replace the responsibilities of researchers and PIs for their own data.

Appendices

Appendix A: CRC1551 Consortium

Project ID	Project Title	Principal Investigator(s)
R01	Intrinsically Disordered to α -Helix Transition of the IM30 Protein Structure	Mischa Bonn Martin Girard Dirk Schneider
R02	Functions of Ubiquitin and SUMO in Protein Phase Separation and Aggregation	Kurt Kremer Oleksandra Kukharenko Helle Ulrich
R03	Targeted Protein Degradation in Nuclear Quality Control Condensates	Petra Beli Kurt Kremer Oleksandra Kukharenko Katja Luck
R04	Regulating Cellular Functions by Light-Gated Assembly of Phase-Separated Nanostructures (Optoaggregates)	Katharina Landfester Axel Methner Tanja Weil
R05	A Supramolecular Chemical Biology Approach to Studying Protein–RNA-Based Regulatory Switches	Pol Besenius Julian König Friederike Schmid
R06	Phase Separation of RS Splicing Regulators as a Modulator of Light-Dependent Plant Development	Friederike Schmid Andreas Wachter
R07	Understanding the Specificity of the Subcellular Organization of Argonaute Proteins	René Ketting Lukas Stelzl
R08	Polymer Concepts Related to Post-translational Modification of Neurodegeneration-Linked RNA-Binding Proteins	Dorothee Dormann Lukas Stelzl
R10	Effect of DNA Topology on SMC Protein-Mediated Loop Extrusion	Eugene Kim Peter Virnau
R11	Investigation of Sequence–Structure Relationships in Interphase Chromatin	Susanne Gerber Susann Schweiger Peter Virnau
R12	Regulation and Role of Physical Properties for Transcriptional Condensates	Sandra Schick-Nickolaus Thomas Speck
R13	DNA-Facilitated Nano-assembly of Biological Block Co-polymers	Martin Girard Edward A. Lemke Sina Wittmann
R14	Protonuclei as Platform to Study Phase Behaviour and Biological Function of Arginine-Glycine (RG)-rich Proteins	Miguel Andrade Dorothee Dormann Andreas Walther
R15	Unraveling multivalent interactions in the pre-synapse	Jasper Michels Carla Schmidt

Continued on next page

Project ID	Project Title	Principal Investigator(s)
R16	Covalent and Non-Covalent Macromolecular Approach for Precision and Switchable Protein Oligomerization: Exploring Fundamental Insights and Control Cellular Functions	Shikha Dhiman
R17	Nucleation dynamics in field theories for intracellular phase separation	Michael te Vrugt
Z01	Biopolymer Engineering and Bioanalytics	Svenja Morsbach Martin Möckel
Z02	Visualization of Biopolymer Function and Research Data Management	Bastian B. Hülsmann Sandra Ritz
Z03	Integrated Research Training Group	Mischa Bonn Ralf Dahm Dorothee Dormann
Z04	Central Tasks of the Collaborative Research Centre	Edward A. Lemke

Appendix B: Definitions

The following terms are used throughout this policy with the meanings given below.

Research data

All data generated, collected, or processed in the course of scientific work, including measurements, observations, simulation outputs, derived datasets, software, and associated documentation. This encompasses both raw and processed data in any format or medium. [1]

Research data lifecycle

The sequence of stages through which research data passes from initial planning and collection through analysis, preservation, and eventual sharing or deletion. The stages addressed in this policy are: Planning, Collection, Analysis, Preservation, Sharing, and Reuse.

Research Data Management (RDM)

The organisation, documentation, storage, preservation, and sharing of data collected and used in research. It encompasses the entire research data lifecycle from planning through reuse.

Good Research Practice (*Gute wissenschaftliche Praxis*)

The set of principles and standards governing the responsible conduct of research, as defined by the DFG Code of Conduct [1] and implemented by the participating institutions [2, 3, 4, 5].

Data Management Plan (DMP)

A structured document describing how research data will be handled during and after a project, covering data types, storage, documentation, sharing, and preservation. Introduced in [Section 5.1.1](#).

Thesis Advisory Committee (TAC)

A committee responsible for supervising doctoral researchers and reviewing their progress, including the status of their data management plan. Introduced in [Section 5.1.1](#).

Electronic Laboratory Notebook (ELN)

A digital system for recording experimental procedures, observations, and results, replacing physical lab notebooks. Enables structured data entry, file attachments, and integration with research workflows.

FAIR principles

A set of principles — Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable — that guide the management and sharing of research data to maximise their value for current and future use [12].

Persistent identifier (PID)

A long-lasting reference to a digital resource, such as a DOI (Digital Object Identifier), that remains stable independent of changes to the resource's location or hosting.

Repository

A managed digital infrastructure for storing, preserving, and providing access to research data or publications, operated by an institution, discipline community, or general-purpose provider.

Metadata

Structured information that describes, contextualises, and enables discovery of research data. Includes descriptive metadata (authorship, subject, keywords), technical metadata (instrument settings, file formats, software versions), and administrative metadata (access rights, licences, retention periods).

Research Data Steward (RDS)

The person appointed within CRC1551 to provide guidance and support on research data management, as defined in [Section 7](#).

Open Access

The principle that research outputs — including publications and data — should be freely accessible online without financial, legal, or technical barriers, consistent with the Berlin Declaration on Open Access [[14](#)].

Appendix C: Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used throughout this policy.

CC Creative Commons — a set of standardised public licences for sharing creative and scientific works.

CC-BY

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International — a permissive licence requiring attribution. See [Open Access](#).

CC0 Creative Commons Zero — public domain dedication waiving all rights.

CRC Collaborative Research Centre (*Sonderforschungsbereich*).

DFG Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft — German Research Foundation.

DMP Data Management Plan. See [Definition](#).

DOI Digital Object Identifier — a persistent identifier for digital resources. See [Persistent identifier](#).

ELN Electronic Laboratory Notebook — a digital system for recording experimental procedures, observations, and results. See [Definition](#).

FAIR Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable. See [Definition](#).

IMB Institute of Molecular Biology gGmbH, Mainz.

IPR Intellectual Property Rights.

JGU Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz (*Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz*).

MPG Max Planck Society (*Max-Planck-Gesellschaft*).

JMUW

Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg — University of Würzburg.

NFDI

National Research Data Infrastructure (*Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur*).

ORCID

Open Researcher and Contributor ID — a persistent identifier for researchers.

PID Persistent Identifier. See [Definition](#).

RDM Research Data Management. See [Definition](#).

RDMO

Research Data Management Organiser — a tool for creating and managing data management plans.

RDS Research Data Steward. See [Definition](#).

TAC Thesis Advisory Committee. See [Definition](#).

Appendix D: Suggested Directory Structure and File Naming

The structure and naming conventions below are recommendations. Groups are encouraged to adapt them to their workflows, provided the chosen system is documented and applied consistently within the group.

D.1 Directory Structure

A project folder should separate raw data from processed data and analysis, and keep documentation alongside the data it describes. [Figure 1](#) illustrates one way to achieve this.

Each subdirectory may contain its own README .md where the contents are not self-explanatory. Raw data directories should be set to read-only after data collection is complete (see [Section 6](#)).

D.2 File Naming

File names should be descriptive, sortable, and unambiguous. The following convention is recommended:

YYYYMMDD_ProjectID_ResearcherIDExperimentNr_Datatype_vNN.ext

- **Date** in ISO 8601 format (YYYYMMDD) at the start ensures chronological sorting. Time (HHMMSS) may be appended if sub-day resolution is needed.
- **ProjectID** links the file to a CRC1551 subproject (e.g. A01, B03)
- **ResearcherIDExperimentNr** combines a short personal identifier (initials) with a zero-padded experiment number (e.g. AMe001 for Anna Meyer, experiment 1). The experiment number increments with each new experiment, not each new file.
- **Datatype** indicates the processing status: rawdata, metadata, processeddata, or graph
- **Version** (v01, v02, ...) tracks iterations of a file; use leading zeros for correct sorting

Examples:

- 20240315_A01_AMe001_rawdata_v01.hdf5
- 20240315_A01_AMe001_processeddata_v01.csv
- 20240318_B03_JKo002_rawdata_v01.tiff
- 20240320_C02_TSc001_rawdata_v01.xtc

Rules:

- Use only letters, digits, hyphens (-), and underscores (_)
- No spaces, no special characters (~ ! @ # \$ % ^ & * () , ; : ' " < > ?)
- No accented characters (e.g. avoid ü, é)
- Keep names under 64 characters where possible
- Reserve periods exclusively for file extensions

Figure 1: Project directory structure

Appendix E: Recommended File Formats

Open, non-proprietary file formats ensure that data remains accessible independently of specific software or vendor licences. The table below lists recommended formats for general data types common across CRC1551 projects. Where proprietary formats must be used during active research (e.g. instrument-native formats), a copy in an open format should be created for archiving and sharing purposes.

Table 2: Recommended file formats for long-term preservation and sharing

Data type	Recommended formats	Avoid for archiving
Plain text	TXT, MD	DOC, DOCX
Formatted documents	PDF/A ¹	DOC, DOCX
Tabular data	CSV, TSV ²	XLS, XLSX
Raster images	TIFF, PNG	JPG, ³ GIF
Structured / hierarchical data	HDF5, ⁴ XML, JSON	proprietary binary formats
Code and scripts	plain text (.py, .r, .sh, .m) ⁵	compiled binaries alone

¹ PDF/A is the archival variant of PDF.

² Include a header row and a README describing column names.

³ JPG is lossy; avoid for scientific images intended for reuse.

⁴ HDF5 is widely used for large scientific datasets.

⁵ Archive with dependencies documented; use Git for version control.

Domain-specific format recommendations (microscopy, sequencing, NMR, MD simulations) are outside the scope of this appendix. Researchers working with instrument-native or discipline-specific formats should refer to the relevant community standards or consult the RDS.

Appendix F: Core Metadata Standard

Metadata **must be created at the point of dataset creation** — not deferred until archiving or publication. A metadata file created early ensures that provenance, authorship, and context are recorded while they are still known, and that the file is updated as the dataset evolves.

CRC1551 uses JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) as the format for dataset metadata files. JSON is both human-readable and machine-readable, making it easy to inspect in any text editor while remaining processable by data management tools and repository systems. Name the file `metadata.json` and place it in the top-level directory of the dataset (see Appendix D).

CRC1551 adopts the **Schema.org Dataset** schema supplemented by **Bioschemas** as its baseline metadata standard, providing a vocabulary that is widely recognised by repositories and search engines. Fill in core fields (name, creator, dateCreated, description) when the dataset is first established. Update the file as the dataset grows or changes. Complete all fields — including identifier, license, and datePublished — when the dataset is deposited in a repository. Replace the placeholder values in the example below with the information for your dataset (see Figure 2).

The `funder` and `isPartOf` fields are the same for all CRC1551 datasets and **must not be changed**. The `identifier` field under `"@type": "Dataset"` is assigned by the repository upon deposit and can be filled in afterwards. An ORCID identifier for each creator can be obtained free of charge at <https://orcid.org>.

```
{
  "@context": "https://schema.org/",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "name": "Widefield fluorescence microscopy of RNA Pol II
  condensates in HeLa cells",
  "description": "Widefield fluorescence images of HeLa cells
  expressing GFP-tagged RNA Polymerase II acquired during
  transcriptional stress. Dataset contains raw .tiff files
  and processed maximum-intensity projections. Cells were
  treated with 1,6-hexanediol at indicated concentrations.",
  "dateCreated": "2024-03-15",
  "datePublished": "2024-06-01",
  "creator": [
    {
      "@type": "Person",
      "name": "Meyer, Anna",
      "identifier": "https://orcid.org/0000-0000-0000-0001"
    }
  ],
  "affiliation": {
    "@type": "Organization",
    "name": "Institute of Molecular Biology Mainz gGmbH"
  },
  "funder": {
    "@type": "Organization",
    "name": "Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG)",
    "identifier": "https://ror.org/018mejw64"
  },
  "isPartOf": {
    "@type": "ResearchProject",
    "name": "CRC1551 Polymer Concepts in Cellular Function",
    "identifier": "Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG)
    - Project number 464588647"
  },
  "keywords": ["RNA Polymerase II", "condensates",
  "fluorescence microscopy", "HeLa cells",
  "transcription", "CRC1551"],
  "license": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/",
  "identifier": "https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.0000000",
  "distribution": {
    "@type": "DataDownload",
    "contentUrl": "https://zenodo.org/record/0000000",
    "encodingFormat": "TIFF"
  },
  "measurementTechnique": "Widefield fluorescence microscopy",
  "variableMeasured": "Fluorescence intensity",
  "isBasedOn": "https://doi.org/10.1000/xyz123",
  "version": "1.0"
}
```

Figure 2: Example Schema.org/Dataset metadata record in JSON-LD format.

Appendix G: Version History

Version 1.1 – 2026-04-16

Author: Andrej Berg

- Title page updated with a document-level licence statement: [CC-BY](#) (Attribution 4.0 International).
- Section 2 expanded with a new “Adoption and review” subsection documenting acceptance of Version 1.0 by opt-out procedure and defining a regular 12-month review cycle with extraordinary review on policy changes.
- Section 5.4.2 repository guidance clarified by naming example institutional repositories: Gutenberg Open Science and EDMOND.
- Appendix A consortium table updated: project Z01 renamed from “Support Project on Biopolymer Engineering and Bioanalytics” to “Biopolymer Engineering and Bioanalytics”.

Version 1.0 – 2026-04-07

Author: Andrej Berg

- Terminology unified: “Good Research Practice” is used consistently throughout the document. Previously “Good Scientific Practice” and “Good Research Practice” appeared as synonyms in several sections.
- All URL footnotes converted to inline hyperlinks to improve navigation in the electronic PDF.
- [FAIR](#) principles explicitly stated as a mandatory component of Good Research Practice within CRC1551; adherence is now binding for all consortium members.
- Labfolder added to the list of recommended [ELN](#) tools; available to members of Max Planck institutes through an institutional [MPG](#) licence.
- Spelling and grammar corrected throughout the document.

Version 0.2 – 2026-03-23

Author: Andrej Berg

- All good-practice boxes filled with concrete, discipline-specific guidance relevant to CRC1551 research workflows
- Appendix B (Definitions) completed: 13 key terms defined with cross-references from body text
- Appendix C (Abbreviations) completed: 20 entries with cross-references from first use in body text
- Appendix D added: Suggested directory structure and file naming conventions, including a worked example
- Appendix E added: Recommended file formats table covering common CRC1551 data types
- Appendix F added: Core metadata standard with a JSON template and lifecycle guidance (create at dataset creation, complete at deposit)
- Appendix G added: Version history in changelog format (this appendix)
- Appendix H added: Standard Operating Procedures, including a Publication Checklist with mandatory and recommended steps
- Layout changed from print (two-sided) to screen-optimised (single-sided) to improve readability as a reference document
- Visual distinction introduced between mandatory requirements (highlighted in red) and recommended practices (highlighted in purple) throughout the policy text

- Section 5 (Data Management Practices) completed: all subsections on Planning, Collection, Analysis, Preservation, Sharing, and Reuse now contain detailed policy guidance
- Defined terms in the policy body now link to their entries in Appendix B; abbreviations link to Appendix C on first use
- All section, subsection, and subsubsection headings assigned reference labels; all cross-references within the document verified and corrected

Version 0.1 — 2026-01-19**Author:** Andrej Berg

- Initial draft of the CRC1551 Research Data Management Policy, covering governance scope, data management requirements, and responsibilities

Appendix H: Publication Checklist

Use this checklist when preparing a journal article or conference paper for submission. Download it into your paper directory at the start of writing and check items off as the paper progresses.

Further reading: RDMkit Data Publication guide — rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/data_publication

Before submission:

- Identify all datasets underlying the results reported in this paper.
- Verify all datasets are documented according to [Section 4](#) and stored on institutional storage.
- Check for legal, ethical, or contractual restrictions on the data (ownership, confidentiality, third-party rights).
- Run quality control on all datasets before deposit.
- Convert data to open formats where required (see [Appendix E](#)).
- Complete the metadata .json file for each dataset (see [Appendix F](#)).
- Select a repository and assign a license (CC0 or CC-BY; see [Section 5.5.2](#) and [Section 3.4](#)).
- Deposit datasets and record the [DOIs](#).
- Write a data availability statement — include repository name, [DOI](#), and license — and add it to the manuscript.
- Include data citations with full [DOIs](#) in the reference list of the manuscript.

Acknowledgements:

- Include the CRC funding sentence in the acknowledgements section:
We acknowledge funding by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) – SFB1551 – Project No. 464588647.
- If core facility instruments were used, include the following sentence (fill in staff name, institution, CF name, support provided, instrument name, and DFG project number):
The authors thank [enter staff name] of the [enter institution & CF name] for their support and assistance with [enter specific support provided] on the [instrument name & project number].

Instruments and their DFG project numbers:

- TCS STED CW Super-Resolution (DFG project #204504610)
- SR GSDIM Super-Resolution (DFG project #212047918)
- AF7000 Widefield (DFG project #212049334)
- Opera Phenix (DFG project #316215830)
- VisiTron Spinning Disc (DFG project #402386039)
- Stellaris 8 Falcon Confocal (DFG project #497669232)
- C-Trap (DFG project #544814404)

After acceptance:

- Fill out the [CRC1551 publication form](#) to register the paper with the consortium.
- Verify that all dataset [DOIs](#) resolve correctly.
- Update the DMP to reflect the published paper and datasets.
- Add the paper [DOI](#) and all dataset [DOIs](#) to your ORCID record.

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